

Micro-econometric Analysis of the Determinants of socio-economic in the use of basic health services in Senegal

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Highlights

- The level of education directly influences people's ability to access and effectively use the health care system.
- Financial accessibility to health services is therefore a problem, as individuals and households find themselves in a vicious circle of chronic poverty

Abstract

Background: In spite of social and economic interventions, state health policies have not yet succeeded in providing households in poor and low-income areas with better chances of survival and better chances of using health services. Health services are part of a larger structure called the health system. The health system is made up of all the elements that determine the health status of a population. The starting point of the health system is the population and more specifically the identification of the health needs of that population.

The objective of this paper is to assess the influence of the different factors determining the use of health services in Senegal.

Health inequities undermine the lives and futures of all vulnerable groups by creating systems of social injustice.

Methods: Since the outcome variable was a dichotomous variable, a discrete choice model was employed to show how the explanatory variables correlated with the outcome variable. Specifically, the binary logistic regression was employed given that this technique is more appropriate for dichotomous variables. A key assumption underlying the binary logistic regression model is that the dependent variable should be dichotomous in nature and the data should not have any outlier.

Results: The results showed that the main finding of the study is that low educational attainment has significant negative effects on health service utilization. In fact, educational attainment is one of the key determinants of health.

Household economic status, which was grouped into four representative modalities from the three explanatory variables, and each of the individuals classified according to these modalities through their income strongly influences the decision to go to the hospital.

Keywords : Determinants , socio-economic , logistic regression,

Introduction

Most community finance schemes have evolved in the context of severe economic constraints, political instability, and lack of good governance. Usually government taxation capacity is weak, formal mechanisms of social protection for vulnerable populations absent, and government oversight of informal health sector lacking. In this context of extreme public sector failure, community involvement in financing health care provides a critical, though insufficient, first step in the long march toward improved health care access for the poor and social protection against the cost of illness.

In any society, health and illness are two fundamental realities since they have an impact on social life as well as on the course of economic life. Households experience the effects of these two realities on a daily basis, which vary at different points in their life course. The way individuals view their health or the illnesses or disorders they face is largely determined by their culture and their membership in social groups.

Findings from all research on the socio-economic determinants of health point to concrete living conditions as structural obstacles that make it difficult to achieve and maintain optimal health. In spite of social and economic interventions, state health policies have not yet succeeded in providing households in poor and low-income areas with better chances of survival and better chances of using health services. Health services are part of a larger structure called the health system. The health system is made up of all the elements that determine the health status of a population. The starting point of the health system is the population and more specifically the identification of the health needs of that population. The response to needs is expressed through the use of health services. Several factors influence the type and level of use of services. These factors relate not only to the individuals who take steps to use services, but also to the characteristics of the system itself. It is increasingly recognized that lifestyle habits, environment and socioeconomic level have a major impact on the health of populations.

Slim Haddad (92) confirm the hypothesis that the usefulness that individuals attribute to different therapeutic alternatives depends on their health needs, their financial capabilities and the costs and benefits they attribute to these different alternatives. Relationships between populations and health care workers are an essential component of perceived benefits. The quality of these relationships has a decisive influence on the attendance of health centers. These results, some of which are relatively innovative, open up various avenues of research that should be explored.

A variety of factors have been identified as the leading causes of poor utilization of primary health care services: including poor socio-economic status, lack of physical accessibility, cultural beliefs and perceptions, low literacy level of the mothers and large family size. Review of the global literature suggests that these factors can be classified as cultural beliefs, socio-demographic status, women's autonomy, economic conditions, physical and financial accessibility, and disease pattern and health service issues (Babar T. Shaikh, (2005)

Mukherjee, S., Haddad, S. & Narayana, D. (2011) examine caste-based inequalities in households' out-of-pocket health expenditure. Caste-based inequality in household health expenditure reflects unequal access to quality health care by different caste groups. Households with high health care needs and chronic health care needs are most affected by this inequality. Households in the most marginalised castes and with high health care need require protection against impoverishing health expenditures. Special emphasis must be given to funding hospitalisation, as this expenditure puts households most at risk in terms of mobilising monetary resources.

Using generalized logit model, Saeed, B.I.I., Yawson, A.E., Nguah, S. et al. (2016). found that health status is a very strong determinant of the type of healthcare services preferred by older adults Ghanaians. Men with higher income preferred the private health facilities, while those who completed tertiary education, those with health insurance and those who self-rated their health as very bad, bad or moderate preferred public facility. Self-employed men and those in informal employment, preferred other health facilities outside the formal public health service. Women with primary and secondary education, preferred the private health facilities. Women with health insurance, those in middle and upper class income quintiles or those with self-rated bad and moderate health status or being relatively younger preferred the public facility to other health services. Self-employed women and those in informal employment preferred traditional treatment. In Ghana, there are important socio-economic gradients in the use of some healthcare services. In both sexes, those without insurance and rural residents preferred the pharmacy and traditional treatment.

Flatø, H., Zhang, H. (2016) demonstrate that assessments of equity should pay attention to inequalities in level of healthcare utilization. Our results indicate that in China, wide insurance coverage is insufficient to ensure equity in level of healthcare utilization. On the contrary, type of insurance enrollment has become a main driver of inequity in level of utilization. Hence,

equalizing health insurance schemes would be of crucial importance in order to improve health equity in China

Wabiri, N., Chersich, M., Shisana, O. *et al.*(2016) describes inequalities over time in access to maternal health services in South Africa, and identifies differences in maternal health outcomes between population groups and across geographical areas. Though some population-level improvements occurred in access to services, inequalities generally worsened. Low levels of planned pregnancy, antenatal clinic access and having a doctor present at childbirth among poor women are of most concern.

Economic status, educational level, insurance coverage and household gender were the most influential factors on health services utilization. Those with a high socio-economic level were more likely to demand and use such services; although self-medication patterns showed an opposite trend. Mohammad Ranjbar and al(2018)

Ilinca, S., Di Giorgio, L., Salari, P. *et al.*(2019). find significant inequality and inequity in the use of all types of care services favouring richer population groups, with particularly pronounced levels for preventive and inpatient care services. These are driven primarily by differences in living standards and educational achievement, while the region of residence is a key driver for inequality in preventive care use only. Pro-rich inequalities are particularly pronounced for care provided in privately owned facilities, while public providers serve a much larger share of individuals from lower socio-economic groups.

Zon, H., Pavlova, M. & Groot, W.(2021) analyze the socio-demographic determinants of households' access to healthcare. The findings indicate an association between age, education, income and use of services. The results show that healthcare users' satisfaction is influenced by age, the association is stronger with the age group than the age group . An association was found between the age group under, the type of health facility used, the distance traveled to health facilities and households' individuals' health expenditure.

Several studies have assessed the household determinants of utilization of health services. These studies have not yielded a consistent pattern of relationships between service utilization and household predictors. In some cases, even when a strong association has been reported, such as in the case of the positive relationship between education and the use of skilled health attendants at birth, the extent and nature of the relationship are not uniform across social settings.

Today the populations in most industrial countries enjoy universal access to a comprehensive range of health services that are financed through a combination of general tax revenues, social insurance, private insurance, and charges (Preker 1998).

The objective of this paper is to assess the influence of the different factors determining the use of health services in Senegal. Health inequities undermine the lives and futures of all vulnerable groups by creating systems of social injustice. By removing barriers that limit access to health services and resources, we reduce the burden of disease that affects and impoverishes entire families and perpetuates social and economic inequality across generations.

The structure of the document is as follows, first the introduction, then description of the methodology, analysis of results, and finally the conclusion

1. Data and methods

1.1 Data sources

Data from the 2019 Demographic and Health Survey (DHS) from Senegal were used for this paper. The 2019 Senegal Continuous Health Care Service Delivery Survey (ECPSS) is the second phase after the pilot of the continuous surveys in Senegal, which was a five-year project (2012-2017). The ECPSS is a survey of health facilities, designed to obtain information on the functioning and quality of services within health facilities offering maternal and child health services, specific infectious disease services, such as Sexually Transmitted Infections (STIs), HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, malaria, blood transfusion services and chronic disease services.

It was conducted on a nationally representative sample of formal health facilities in the 14 regions of the country. Health service administrators and providers in the health facilities visited were interviewed; providers and patients who came for specific health services (consultation of sick children under five and family planning) were observed during consultations; and interviews were conducted with patients and/or caregivers of sick children whose consultations were observed.

1.2 Study variables

The social determinants of health (SDH) are the non-medical factors that influence health outcomes. They are the conditions in which people are born, grow, work, live, and age, and the wider set of forces and systems shaping the conditions of daily life. These forces and systems include economic policies and systems, development agendas, social norms, social policies and political systems. The SDH have an important influence on health inequities - the unfair and avoidable differences in health status seen within and between countries. In countries at all levels of income, health and illness follow a social gradient: the lower the socioeconomic position, the worse the health¹. The outcome variable employed for this study was visited health. The outcome variable was derived from the questions do you "Visited health facility last 12 months" ? (No, Yes). The 'Yes' responses were coded '1' and the 'No' responses were coded '0'. Seven explanatory variables were used in the study age, wealth index, education, residence, occupation, getting money needed for treatment, distance to health facility . Age was recoded as "15-19", "20-24", "25-29", "30-34", "35-39", "40-44" and "45-49". Wealth status was categorized in poorest, poorer, middle, richer and richest. Education was classified into four categories: no education, primary education, secondary education , higher education

¹ World Health Organisation Social Determinants of Health. Overview. [(accessed on 13 January 2021)]. Available online: https://www.who.int/health-topics/social-determinants-of-health#tab=tab_1

and others. Occupation was captured as not working, professional/technical/managerial, clerical, sales, agricultural, household and domestic, services, skilled manual, unskilled manual and others.

Getting money needed for treatment was categorized in big problem, not a big problem. Distance to health facility was categorized in big problem, not a big problem. Type of residence was coded as urban or rural.

1.3 Data analysis

Logistic regression is a widely used method because it makes it possible to model binomial variables (typically binary), multinomial (qualitative variables with more than two modalities) or ordinal (qualitative variables whose modalities can be ordered). Since the outcome variable was a dichotomous variable, a discrete choice model was employed to show how the explanatory variables correlated with the outcome variable. Specifically, the binary logistic regression was employed given that this technique is more appropriate for dichotomous variables. A key assumption underlying the binary logistic regression model is that the dependent variable should be dichotomous in nature and the data should not have any outlier.

2. Analysis

Tableau N°1 : Binary logistic regression

Visit health	Coef.	St.Err.	t-value	p-value	[95% Conf	Interval]	Sig
Age	.008	.004	1.83	.067	-.001	.017	*
Educational level		
Primary	-.107	.045	-2.39	.017	-.195	-.019	**
Secondary	-.364	.067	-5.39	0	-.496	-.231	***
Higher	-.146	.196	-0.74	.457	-.53	.239	
Others	-12.659	527.195	-0.02	.981	-1045.942	1020.623	
Wealth index	0	
Poorer	-.347	.043	-8.05	0	-.432	-.263	***
Middle	-.491	.047	-10.40	0	-.584	-.399	***
Richer	-.906	.054	-16.75	0	-1.012	-.8	***
Richest	-.868	.063	-13.74	0	-.992	-.744	***
Constant	-.919	.088	-10.40	0	-1.092	-.746	***
Mean dependent var	0.770		SD dependent var	0.421			
Pseudo r-squared	0.021		Number of obs	21562.000			
Chi-square	484.469		Prob > chi2	0.000			
Akaike crit. (AIC)	22778.566		Bayesian crit. (BIC)	22858.353			

*** $p < .01$, ** $p < .05$, * $p < .1$

Source : Author

Looking at the table above, we can say that the econometric analysis confirms the significance of the variables as well as the sign of their their effect on the decision to go to the hospital.

For the education level variable, we distinguish three For this variable, we distinguish three modalities (primary, secondary and higher education).

Each of these modalities, theoretically, is a determinant of the household's behavior, including its decision to first go to the hospital in case of illness instead of seeking traditional treatment and, in case of aggravation of the illness go to a health center.

The main finding of the study is that low educational attainment has significant negative effects on health service utilization. In fact, educational attainment is one of the key determinants of health. Regardless of the reasons for consultation, people with low education use fewer health services than those with higher reading skills. Educational attainment is an important factor influencing most decisions to use health services. The level of education directly influences people's ability to access and effectively use the health care system.

People with low literacy skills have limited access to health information, both written and verbal. Most health information from health organizations and practitioners, as well as from other sources such as the media, is in written form and is difficult or impossible for many people to understand. In addition, many people do not trust written information and prefer to get their health information by word of mouth. As a result, many people with low literacy skills do not know where to go to receive the health services they need. Lack of information and limited resources often result in people neglecting preventive care and waiting for their health problems to worsen before seeing a health professional. health care professional.

Household economic status, which was grouped into four representative modalities form the three explanatory variables, and each of the individuals classified according to these modalities through their income strongly influences the decision to go to the hospital.

This notion cannot be appreciated without approaching it in the current socio-economic context. All observers agree that the Senegalese people live today in a context of chronic poverty.

However, the Senegal Poverty Monitoring Survey conducted in 2005 reveals that 50.8% of Senegalese still live below the poverty line, with significant geographic and spatial.

Financial accessibility to health services is therefore a problem, as individuals and households find themselves in a vicious circle of chronic poverty. It must be recognized that even if the consultation fees are not very high, the envelope is not limited to the consultation not limited

to the consultation; analyses, medicines, transport of the patient and the accompanying person are added to it, thus making the care out of reach of the patients.

In addition, certain pathologies require scans for diagnosis, the high cost of which is often out of reach for patients. These difficulties very often explain the delay of Senegalese to consult or not to consult a doctor.

Conclusion

Facilitating access to primary health care and ensuring universal health coverage for the population remains a major challenge for developing countries.

Indeed, despite some efforts made in recent decades, the problem of access to health care is far from being resolved. In addition to the thorny problem of human resources, there are difficulties related to the organization and functioning of health systems, the financing of health systems, the provision of quality care and access to basic medicines.

All of this has a disastrous impact on the population, particularly the poorest, who are no longer able to benefit from quality care that allows them to obtain optimal health.

The main finding of the study is that low educational attainment has significant negative effects on health service utilization. In fact, educational attainment is one of the key determinants of health.

Household economic status, which was grouped into four representative modalities from the three explanatory variables, and each of the individuals classified according to these modalities through their income strongly influences the decision to go to the hospital.

Whatever the approach considered, it seems necessary to carry out a broader reflection on the causes of social and economic inequalities in health and on the means to remedy them.

It is necessary to pursue and develop research on the factors that explain the barriers to access to care, and on the social, economic and psycho-socio-economic determinants of health status, in order to develop and implement appropriate health policies and programs, possibly targeted according to these factors.

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